

Mastoid Antral Changes in Mucosal Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media**Manoj Kumar¹, Amrita Srivastava², Surendra Kumar Kanaujia³, Nishant Saurabh Saxena⁴, Ashok Kumar Verma⁵, Chayanika Kala⁶, Shiroman Singh⁷**¹Junior Resident, Department of ENT, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur²Associate Professor, Department of ENT, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur³Professor and Head, Department of ENT, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur⁴Associate Professor, Department of ENT, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur⁵Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur⁶Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur, India⁷Professor, Central research centre, GSVM Medical College, Kanpur, India

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Abstract**Objective:** To correlate preoperative radiological and intra-operative pathological mastoid antrum findings in mucosal type of CSOM. This study examines the radio-pathological changes in the mastoid antrum to enhance diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient management for better prognosis and reduced complications.**Methodology:** We examined 119 ENT patients of inactive mucosal CSOM, who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were subjected to array of investigations like, PTA and HRCT Temporal bone. Patients were subjected to tympanoplasty in combination with antrostomy or cortical mastoidectomy. Intraoperative findings were recorded and association between radiological and intraoperative pathological antral findings was sought using statistical tests.**Results:** Mastoid antrum was found to be diseased in 42 patients. Pathologies observed in the mastoid antrum included hyperplastic mucosa, granulation tissue, cholesteatoma, etc.**Conclusion:** The study analysed preoperative and intraoperative findings of mastoid antrum and identified strong correlation between the two particularly with middle ear mucosa condition, hearing loss, mastoid pneumatization, ossicular chain status, aditus patency and recurrent URTIs.**Keywords:** Chronic suppurative otitis media, mastoid antrum, aditus, antrostomy, cortical mastoidectomy.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) mucosal variety typically arises from infections originating in the oropharynx and nasopharynx, often following an acute episode of otitis media (AOM). The mucosa of the middle ear cleft's anteroinferior region is more frequently affected. Tympanosclerosis, adhesions, ossicular chain erosion and polypoidal alterations of the mucosa are pathological abnormalities in the mucosal form of CSOM. Complications are uncommon in mucosal type. [1]

Situated just behind the ear, in the mastoid process of the temporal bone, are a network of tiny, air-filled cavities known as the mastoid air cells.

The integrity and well-being of these air cells are crucial for appropriate ventilation of the middle ear. [2] The middle ear system's volume is greatly increased by an aerated mastoid, which helps to reduce pressure variations in the middle ear cavity. [3]

The function of the eustachian tube (ET), the patency of tympanic isthmus, aditus ad antrum, the posterior epitympanum, the volume of the mastoid antrum, and the state of the middle ear cleft mucosa are the main variables regulating this ventilation. [4]

Obstruction of the aditus ad antrum can play a significant role in the development and exacerbation of pathological conditions associated with otitis media. [5-7]

In order to obtain a dry and secure ear, tympanic membrane perforation is managed with tympanoplasty. Nonetheless, a patient may already have pathological modifications in the mastoid antrum. The illness may have an impact on the surgical result if the mastoid antrum is not assessed and cleaned. [1]

The decision to undertake a mastoidectomy in safe and dry ears is not predetermined by any specific rules. Mastoid exploration is supported by those who contend that it improves mastoid aeration and

aids in obtaining aditus patency in mucosal variant of CSOM.

However, opponents believe that the potential risks, such as injury to the middle and inner ear structures, may outweigh these benefits.

The study aims to evaluate radio-pathological mastoid antrum findings in patients of mucosal type of CSOM.

Material and Methods

Study Design: Descriptive observational single center study was conducted in the department of Ear, Nose and Throat, of a tertiary care centre of Kanpur.

Study Population: Patients attending the OPD and IPD of ENT department.

Duration of study: 18 months.

Inclusion Criteria: All cases of inactive mucosal disease in age group of 18–50 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Age <18 and >50 years
- Patient with active mucosal and squamous type of CSOM.
- Patients with a previous history of ear surgery and ear trauma.

Study Methodology

Informed consent was obtained from all participants following approval from the institution's ethics committee with reference number EC/304/Nov/2023.

Patients with confirmed diagnosis of inactive mucosal CSOM were included in the study.

Detailed history, thorough ENT and systemic examination of patients were obtained.

All the patients were subjected to otoscopic examination followed by audiological assessment via Pure Tone Audiometry (PTA) and HRCT Temporal bone.

PTA results were evaluated, and hearing loss was classified according to ASHA classification of hearing impairment [8].

All patients underwent Tympanoplasty in combination with mastoid exploration in form of antrostomy or cortical mastoidectomy.

Intraoperative findings like middle ear mucosa, ossicular chain status, mastoid antrum findings and status of aditus patency were recorded in all patients. Tissue from the antrum was collected and sent for histopathological examination.

The study's reliability was ensured by using recently calibrated equipment and maintaining consistent criteria. Additionally, standardized

procedures during audiological evaluation were used, enhancing repeatability, and ensuring consistency in the evaluation process.

The categorical data obtained from the case sheet was recorded and tabulated in MS excel worksheet and analyzed by using SPSS software/ window excel. Chi square tests were applied and significant findings recorded.

The statistical analysis aimed to provide insights into the radio-pathological status of these patients.

Results

Demographic Profile

Out of 119 Mucosal CSOM cases, the majority were in the age bracket of 21-30 years (32.8%).

Females 84 (70.6%) outnumbered males 35(29.4%), with a male-to-female ratio of 1:2.4. Rural areas accounted for most of the cases, 73(61.3%) surpassing those in urban areas 46 (38.7%).

Clinical Profile

Primary complaints of the patients were ear discharge and hearing loss seen in 100% cases.

Otorrhea

Our study revealed that mucopurulent discharge was most prevalent.

No of Patients

86(72.27%)
33(27.73%)

Nature of discharge

mucopurulent
mucoid

Majority 67(56.30%) patients had otorrhea between 1-5 years duration.

Otoscopy:

Otoscopy revealed that 57(47.90%) patients had medium sized central perforation followed by large perforations that occurred in 33(27.73%) of patients. Only 29(24.37%) patients had small central perforation. However, in our study we did not find a strong correlation between size of perforation and antral status of the patient.

Middle Ear Mucosa:

Among 27(22.68%) patients out of 119, with diseased middle ear mucosa, 9 had oedematous mucosa, 6 hyperplastic mucosa, polypoidal mucosa was seen in 5 cases, 3 had granulation tissue and tympanosclerosis each while 1 patient had in growing epithelium.

Ossicular Status:

Out of 119 patients, only 18(15.13%) had ossicular necrosis.

No of Patients	Ossicle involved
7(5.88%)	handle of mal leus
3(2.52%)	long + lenticular process of incus
1(0.84%)	stapes supra-structure and long process of incus
6(6.04%)	lenticular process of incus
1(0.84%)	stapes supra-structure

Audiological Profile

In our study 97(81.51%) patients had conductive hearing loss whereas 22(18.49%) patients' complaint of mixed hearing loss. None experienced sensorineural deafness.

We used ASHA criteria to determine degree of hearing loss. Majority experienced mild degree of hearing impairment 55(46.21%).

Radiological Profile (HRCT Temporal Bone)

71 patients (59.66%) had pneumatized mastoid air cells, 39 (32.77%) diploic and 9 (7.57%) had sclerotic type of mastoid air cell on HRCT Temporal bone.

No of Patients	Antral status
82 cases (68.91%)	Healthy
37 cases (31.09%)	Soft tissue density mass

Intra-Operative Antral and Aditus Status

In present study we observed that 80(67.22%) patients had patent aditus while it was found blocked in 39(32.78%) patients. Antrum was found diseased in 42 ears.

Histopathological report of diseased antral tissue

Fig 1: Histopathology of Diseased Antral mucosa

Histopathology revealed 12 cases of hyperplastic mucosa followed by 8 cases of edematous mucosa, 7 granulation tissue, 5 polypoidal mucosa, 4 tympanosclerosis, 3 ears with glue, 2 cases of cholesterol granuloma and in 1 case cholesteatoma was found.

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Relationship Of Mastoid Antrum with Various Clinical Parameters

1. Relationship Between Frequency of Urti and Mastoid Antrum

FREQUENT URTI vs Radiological ANTRAL FINDING

No. of cases	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P value
102(85.71%)	78(76.47%)	24(23.53%)	<0.001

FREQUENT URTI vs INTRA-OPERATIVE ANTRAL FINDING

No. of cases	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P value
102(85.71%)	73(71.56%)	29(28.44%)	<0.001

Recurrent upper respiratory tract infections were strongly associated with the patient's antral status with p value less than 0.001.

2. Relationship Between Hearing Loss and Antrum Status

Table 1: Showing relation of Mastoid antrum with hearing impairment

Degree of Hearing Loss (dB)	No. of cases n=119	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P – value
Radiological Antral Finding				
Mild	55(46.21%)	46(83.63%)	09(16.37%)	<0.001
Moderate	43(36.13%)	25(58.13%)	18(41.87%)	
Moderately Severe	19(15.96%)	10(52.63%)	09(47.37%)	
Severe	02(01.68%)	01(50.00%)	01(50.00%)	
Profound	0	0	0	
Intra-Operative Antral Finding				
Mild	55(46.21%)	44(80%)	11(20%)	<0.05
Moderate	43(36.13%)	21(48.83%)	22(51.17%)	
Moderately Severe	19(15.96%)	11(57.89%)	8(42.11%)	
Severe	02(01.68%)	1(50%)	1(50%)	
Profound	0	0	0	

There was no significant association between type of hearing loss and antral status however degree of

hearing loss was significantly associated with antral status.

3. Relationship Between Ossicular Status and Antrum Findings

Table 2: Showing relation of Mastoid antrum with ossicular integrity

Ossicular status	No. of cases n=119	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P – value
Radiological Antral Finding				
Intact	101(82.87%)	78(77.22%)	23(22.78%)	<0.001
Eroded	18(15.13%)	4(22.22%)	14(77.78%)	
Intra-Operative Antral Finding				
Intact	101(84.87%)	75(74.26%)	26(25.74%)	
Eroded	18(15.12%)	02(11.11%)	16(88.89%)	

HRCT Temporal bone as well as intra-operative findings revealed that diseased antrum was found

more in patients with ossicular discontinuity. Highly significant association of ossicular chain integrity with radiological and intraoperative antral status was found with p value < 0.001.

4. Relationship Between Middle Ear Mucosa and Antrum Findings

Table 3: Showing relation of Mastoid antrum with middle ear mucosa

Middle ear mucosa status	No. of cases n=119	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P – value
Radiological Antral Finding				
Healthy	92(77.31%)	78(84.78%)	14(15.22%)	<0.001
Diseased	27(22.69%)	4(14.81%)	23(85.19%)	
Intra-Operative Antral Finding				
Healthy	92(77.31%)	75(81.52%)	17(18.48%)	<0.001
Diseased	27(22.69%)	2(7.40%)	25(92.60%)	

Diseased middle ear mucosa had a direct impact on the condition of mastoid antrum. Highly significant

association was found for both radiological and intraoperative antral status.

5. Relationship Between Mastoid Pneumatisation and Antrum Findings

Figure 2: Antral status vs mastoid pneumatization on HRCT Temporal bone

Figure 3: Intra-operative Antral status vs mastoid pneumatization

It was observed both radiologically and intra-operative that sclerotic mastoids had more diseased antrum as compared to well pneumatised air cell

system. Since p value for the given data was less than 0.001, the above association is highly significant.

6. Relationship Between Aditus Patency and Antrum Findings

Table 4: Showing relation of Mastoid antrum with aditus patency

Aditus status	No. of cases n=119	Healthy antrum	Diseased antrum	P – value
Radiological Antral Finding				
Patent	80(67.22%)	74(92.50%)	06(7.50%)	<0.001
Blocked	39(32.78%)	08(20.51%)	31(79.49%)	
Intra-Operative Antral Finding				
Patent	80(67.22%)	75(93.75%)	05(6.25%)	
Blocked	39(32.78%)	2(5.13%)	37(94.87%)	

About 80% diseased antrum on CT scan and around 95% intra-op unhealthy antrum had blocked

aditus. Aditus patency was thus highly correlated with (P<0.001) with antral disease status.

7. Correlation Between Radiological and Intraoperative Antrum Findings

Table 5: Showing relation of Mastoid antrum on HRCT Temporal bone vs intra-operative antral finding

Radiological antrum findings	Total	Intraoperative antrum findings	
		Healthy	Diseased
Healthy	82	77(93.90%)	05(06.10%)
Diseased	37	0	37(100%)
Total	119	77	42

Radiologically healthy antrum was found in 82 cases. Of these 77 had healthy findings intraoperatively while in 5 cases contradictory findings of diseased antrum was found intraoperatively.

Correlation of 2 findings was found to be significant with $p = 0.00001$.

Discussion

Clinical Profile: In our study the age ranged from 18 to 50 years. The average age of patients was 33.65 years. Maximum patients belonged to age group of 21-30 years. This was in accordance with the study of Palukri S et al. [9]

Our female preponderance was similar to the study of Sharma A et al. [10]

In accordance with the study of Rishabhadda et al [1]. our study also had majority 73(61.35%) patients belonging to urban regions.

The predominant complaint in our study was that of ear discharge and hearing loss in 100% cases. This was comparable to study of Rathiet al. [11]

In a study conducted by Salem et al. [12] in children, upper respiratory infections are strongly correlated with the incidence of CSOM In our study, recurrent upper respiratory tract infections were strongly associated with the patient's antral status.

In our study majority 57(47.90%) patients had medium sized central perforation. However, we did not find a strong correlation between size of perforation and antral status of the patient. In a similar study conducted by Kandel et al. [13], the size of the perforation was not statistically linked to the patient's antral status. In contrast, study conducted by Chakraborty et al. [14] subtotal perforation was found to be strongly correlated with diseased antrum and aditus blockage.

Out of total 18(15.13%) patients with eroded ossicles, 14(77.78%) amongst them had diseased antrum radiologically while 16(88.89%) amongst them had diseased antrum on intraoperative pathology. We found highly significant association between antral and ossicular chain status with radiological and intraoperative pathology. Our results were consistent with the observations of George MV et al. [15]

Our study revealed 27(22.68%) patients had diseased middle ear mucosa. 85.19% patients with diseased antrum had diseased mucosa. Middle ear mucosal status was strongly associated with antral status. The results were consistent with observations of Agarwalet al. [16], Panigrahi et al. [17], Lakhawat et al. [18] and Gargava et al. [19], Sourabh Shankar C et al. [20].

HRCT Temporal bone mastoid pneumatization was very highly significantly associated with antral status. 6(66.67%) (radiologically) and 7(77.78%) (intraoperatively) patients with sclerotic mastoid had diseased antrum. Our results are similar to the studies of Sharma A et al. [10], Roy et al. [21] Hazemet al. [22]

In present study we observed that 80(67.22%) patients had patent aditus while it was found blocked in 39(32.78%) patients. 3 patients (7.49%), radiologically and 37(94.88%), intraoperatively, with blocked aditus had diseased antrum. Status of aditus patency was highly correlated with ($P < 0.001$) with antral disease status. Our results are similar to the results of Bahgat et al [23], Lakhawat et al. [18], Thakur et al. [24], Sourabh Shankar C et al. [20] Chakraborty et al. [14] who found a similar significant association between aditus patency and antral disease.

Hyperplastic mucosa was the most common pathology encountered. Similar results were obtained by Rickers et al. [25] and George MV et al. [15]

Conclusion

The goal in managing CSOM is to thoroughly eradicate the disease from the middle ear cleft to enhance post-operative outcomes. Surgeons may discover a variety of pathologies in the mastoid antrum even when the disease is deemed safe. Therefore, surgical intervention must also address any disease present in the mastoid. By integrating radiological and pathological findings, we can achieve a more comprehensive understanding of mastoid antral changes in mucosal CSOM, leading to better patient management and outcome.

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Ethical approval: Institutional ethical approval was taken for the study.

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